

CONSERVATIONAL STUDIES ON CHLOROPHYTUM BORIVILIANUM (SAFED MUSLI) IN NANDURBAR DISTRICT, MAHARASHTRA-INDIA

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Abstract: *An ethno-ecological and ethno-medicinal survey was conducted in various parts of Nandurbar dist. of Maharashtra to find out the cause of loss of biodiversity and abundance of Chlorophytum borivilianum. Investigation are proceeds to tracing and finding the alternative ways to conservation of Chlorophytum borivilianumat their natural as well as to introductions as a crop in agricultural sector due to huge ethno economic prospective.*

Key Words: Chlorophytum borivilianum, medicinal uses, indigenous and biodiversity

1. INTRODUCTION

All medicinal plants are the most important source of life saving drugs for the majority of the world's population. The WHO estimated that 80 % of the world's population depends on traditional medicines for meeting their primary health care needs (Deore and Khadabadi 2010). India is known for its nature wealth and inventions in the field of medicine, especially 'Aayurveda' which is the identity of India in the world. As well as traditional and folklore medicine system from generation to generation is rich in domestic recipes and communal practice.

Encompassing concepts and methods for the protection and restoration of health, traditional medicine has served as alternative medicine, new pharmaceuticals, and healthcare products.

In India, Chlorophytum species now cultivated in parts of Gujarat, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Uttar Pradesh, Haryana and Karnataka in tropical and sub-tropical climates with altitude up to 1500 m due to demand and its indigenous loss. It is being grown on an area more than 400 hectares for its tuberous roots (Kothari et. al. 2003) and also grow naturally in most forest parts of central India where climates conditions are suitable. This plant can grow well in a range of temperature and rainfall condition. A sandy loamy soil with adequate drainage is ideal for its production. Normal pH range 6 to 7, higher dose of super phosphate, decomposed farmyard manure and good drainage system facilitates better tuber growth. It is usually found in soils rich in organic matter and require bright sunlight (Haqueet. al. 2011).

Chlorophytum is a wonderful medicinal herb belonging to the family Liliaceae commonly known as 'Safedmusli' (Indian vernacular name) comprises three Chlorophytum species, namely, *C. arundinaceum* Baker, *C. tuberosum* Baker and *C. borivilianum* Sant (Singh and Chauhan 2003). A species *C. borivilianum* is a herbaceous with a condensed stem disc from which a whorl of leaves originates. Leaves are sessile, 10–40 cm in length and 0.6–4.0 cm in breadth. The inflorescence raceme and flowers pedicellate with joints. The perianth consists of six tepals, androecium consists of six stamens arranged opposite to tepals. Anthers are longer

than filaments. The fruit is a capsule, which is trilobed and bears 3–12 seeds inside.

The seeds are black and flat. The fibrous roots of the plant are modified into fascicular roots (fleshy root), comprising the economically useful part (Singh et. al. 2003). The medicinal plants board has recognized Safed musli as 6th important herb to be protected and promoted. The board encourages mainstream cultivation of Safed musli by farmers by extending a subsidy of 20 % through National Horticultural board on project cost. *C. borivillianum* is a plant well known for its aphrodisiac as well as immunodialatory activity (Mayanket. al. 2011). *C. borivillianum* is traditionally used for treating oligospermia, pre- and postnatal infections, arthritis, diabetes and dysuria (Kokate, 1994). Its antiviral, anticancer, immunomodulatory, antidiabetic, and anti – inflammatory properties have been evaluated (Mayanket. al. 2011).

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Present study was carried out regarding overexploitations of important medicinal plant Safed Musli. During various field surveys 2013-2014, of different villages from hilly area of Nandurbar district. Open-ended, semi-structured questionnaires were prepared for gathering information on collection, method of utilization, harvesting methods, preparation, and administration of *Chlorophytum borivillianum*, along with other field information on herbal practice. Authentic informants were interviewed randomly but independently from home to home during prearranged appointments.

Chlorophytum borivillianum Santapau & Fernad. (Liliaceae)

Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were held at main camps of each village where the respondents permitted to views information freely, especially in the case of over utilization of *Chlorophytum borivillianum*, facing 'Rare' category in red data book. This information was captured by use of a portable tape recorder. Field excursions were carried out with the help of authentic traditional utilization of plant. Plant materials were collected and voucher specimens deposited in department of Botany, J.E.S. s' Arts, Science and Commerce College Nandurbar-425412 (MS). Information resulting from personal observation also was recorded. After getting information from each location, awareness is given in each visit to each field surveys, regarding conservations of plants with special reference to *Chlorophytum borivillianum*. Through the help of the local administrators, herbal practitioners in different administrative locations were mobilized to form conservation of plants in different groups.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result of the various surveys and meeting regarding overexploitation of *Chlorophytum borivillianum* (Safed Musli) giving two main important conditions that is its 'medicinal important and way of utilization from natural habitat' regarding studied plant and due to both of them biodiversity of this indigenous plant facing very serious circumstances.

Medicinal uses of studied plant are in various cease major are like root use as nutritional tonic during the pregnancy, premature ejaculation and in all general sexual weakness. Due to important therapeutic benefits of plant indigenous peoples are used to sole in local market also. In this all scenario its find out that at the time collection and harvesting of *Chlorophytum borivillianum* proper methods are not utilized.

Chlorophytum borivillianum herb in nature and mostly part used as root or rhizome, facing "Rare" category in RDB (Red Data Book) Status (Nayar and Sastry, 1988). It may due to immature harvesting from natural habitat, complete uprooting of plant body where some time small root/rhizome is required, over utilization in folk and traditional medicine and use to sole in local market as economical prospective. It also find out that due to large demand of plant some peoples are introduced as a crop in agriculture. Most probably that all may be the

criteria which decreases density and diversity of *Chlorophytum borivillianum* in natural habitat, beside this other factor may also be responsible like seeds dormancy which is about 10 months and germinate in the next growing season, rainfall, temperature, deforestation and human civilization in the studied area but that is in minor acceptance. To conserve local biodiversity and abundance of the plant, it's important to introduce wild plants to crop with their sustainable harvesting and its awareness among the local peoples.

4. CONCLUSION

The studied plants are rare species in India for which due conservation efforts are needed to ensure proper utilization. Gatherers usually collect immature and small sized tubers from the nearby forests before fruiting by direct uprooting of the whole plant. Due to the absence of commercially traded species *C. borivillianum* in the natural forests, collectors resort to other species of Musli like *C. tuberosum*, *C. arundinaceum* etc. Misidentification of species was also observed among middlemen and traders' level. Collections of roots from the forest should be done before seed maturity, thus hampering natural regeneration, positioning the species in the rare category in nature (Nayar and Sastry, 1988). The conclusion of the work suggests harvesting at complete maturation that is from November onward gives good collection. But a small few tubers should be left for further generation, start cultivation for economical purpose in farms. It should be necessary to organize awareness camps for cultivation of *Chlorophytum borivillianum* and its harvesting methods from forest department time to time. Besides this, systematic programs are required to be undertaken for creating awareness about loss of biodiversity at the field level. The best time for planting is 25 June to 5 July based on sprouting percentage of the dormant buds (Shrivastava et al., 2001).

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